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Current Trends and Future Tasks of Christian Theology of Asia: In Celebration of the 50th Anniversary of the Foundation of the FABC

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Abstract: This essay begins with a brief assessment of the theological legacy of the Federation of Asian Bishops' Conferences in terms of a triple dialogue (with the Asian poor, cultures, and religions) and contextual theology. It then surveys eight common features of Asian Christianity, namely, foreign character, colonial heritage, dehumanizing poverty, ecological destruction, minority status, Communist and socialist governments, ubiquitous migration, and anti-woman ideology. Next, it points to eight contemporary theological trends in response to these eight commonalities. It concludes with an examination of one of these eight trends, namely, interreligious dialogue, with reference to Pope Francis's teaching on this theme.

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This article discusses the current trends and the future tasks of Asian Christian theology. By way of introduction, in celebration of the 50th anniversary of the founding of the FABC, I briefly assess its theological legacy and its impact on the way theology is being done in Asia today. In light of these achievements, I next outline the current trends in Asian theology and discuss its future orientations. In the final part, I focus on an especially urgent task for the Asian Churches, namely, interreligious dialogue, by examining the teaching of Pope Francis on this theme.¹

The Theological Legacy of the FABC

Fifty years, a long time in a person's life, is but a blip on the Church's two-thousand-year-long historical radar. Yet, the FABC's golden jubilee marks a momentous event in the history of Asian Catholicism, worthy of thankful and joyful celebration, for the impact it has had on the Asian Catholic Churches. As its website states, the FABC is a voluntary association of episcopal conferences in South, East, Southeast, and Central Asia, whose purpose is to

¹ This is a revised article based on an online presentation to Bishops and theologians on the occasion of the 50th anniversary of the founding of Federation of Asian Bishop's Conference (FABC). Allow me to begin by expressing my deepest thanks to Rev. Dr. Francis Gonsalves, SJ, Executive Secretary of the Commission for Theology & Doctrine of the Conference of Catholic Bishops of India, for the kind invitation to address you today. I have been to India twice and on both occasions have been deeply edified by its rich and varied cultures and the profound religiosity of its people. Theologically, I gratefully acknowledge my indebtedness to the Federation of the Asian Bishops' Conferences, the 50th anniversary of which we are celebrating, to Indian Catholic theologians, in particular Raimon Panikkar, the Belgian Jacques Dupuis, Michael Amaladoss, Francis D'Sa, Felix Wilfred, and to the Sri Lankan Jesuit Aloysius Pieris. I dedicate my humble lecture to the memory of the many Indian victims of Covid-19, especially those who selflessly sacrificed their lives to the service of the sick and the dying.

foster among its members solidarity and co-responsibility for the welfare of the Church and society in Asia and to promote and defend the common good. On the occasion of the 50th anniversary of the Asian Bishop's Meeting in Manila in 1970, which was the beginning of the FABC, its Central Secretariat brought out a collection of the Final Statements of all the eleven Plenary Assemblies of the FABC that were held so far and the statements of the 1970 Asian Bishops' Meeting.²

Here is not the place to narrate the FABC's historical development and evaluate its pastoral and theological achievements as well as the significance of the hundreds of "Papers" published by its various Offices.³ The most groundbreaking concept of their theology, in my judgment, is the understanding of the Church's mission as dialogue, indeed a triple dialogue: dialogue with the Asian poor (liberation and integral development), dialogue with Asian cultures (inculturation), and dialogue with the believers of other religions (interreligious encounter).⁴ All the theological statements of the FABC may be viewed as but variations on this leitmotif, by enlarging the category of the poor to include not only the economically poor but also the victims of political oppression, the culturally marginalized, the Dalits, the Adivasis, ethnic and religious minorities, subjugated women and exploited children, migrants, and the ecological destruction of Earth itself; by exploring the diverse ways in which the Christian faith can be expressed employing the various elements of Asian cultures including philosophy, the plastic arts, music, dance, and architecture; and by

² See Vimal Tirimanna (ed.), *Fifty Years of Asian Pastoral Guidance*. Hong Kong: FABC Central Secretariat, 2020.

³ For a brief history and evaluation of the FABC, see Jonathan Tan, *The Federation of Asian Bishops' Conferences (FABC): Bearing Witness to the Gospel and the Reign of God in Asia* (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2021). See also the many writings on the FABC by James H. Kroeger.

⁴ This triple dialogue was first explicitly mentioned at the FABC's First Plenary Assembly in 1974. See Vimal Titimanna, 5-8.

undertaking dialogue with Asian religions such as Hinduism, Buddhism, the Chinese religious traditions, and Islam through common living, collaboration for the common welfare of society, theological discussion, and sharing religious experiences. The concrete and specific modalities of liberation, inculturation, and interreligious encounter may be different, depending on who the poor, cultures, and religions are in various places and at different times, but dialogue as the way to fulfill Christian mission in Asia remains the *cantus firmus* of the FABC's polyphonic theological composition.

In addition to this thematic unity, the most radical and game-changing shift in the FABC's theology as *fides quaerens intellectum* is its adoption of "contexts" as the resources and the starting point of theological reflection.⁵ Contexts are not simply the milieus in which theology is done, as was the case with Western classical, say, Thomas Aquinas's, theology; rather they are the "signs of the time" that serve as the hermeneutical lens to interpret Scripture and Tradition. Of course, Scripture and Tradition are used to shed light on the signs of the times but conversely, the signs of the time shape the interpretation of these Christian sources. Thus, there is no doubt in the FABC's documents about where, when, and how theology is done and who are its agents. Significantly, all its statements invariably begin with an exposition of the socio-political, economic, cultural, and religious contexts and only then proceed to elucidate the Christian message in the light of and for these contexts. Adopting this theological methodology, I now highlight some salient features of the contexts in which I think Asian Christian theology should be elaborated.

⁵ On this understanding of "context," see Franz-Josef Eilers, ed., *For All the Peoples of Asia: Federation of Asian Bishops' Conference Documents from 1997 to 2001*, vol. 3. Quezon City, The Philippines: Claretian Publications, 2002, 355-364.

Contextual Elements of Asian Christianity

Culturally, there are two dominant cultures in Asia, the Indic and the Sinic, the former predominantly in South Asia, and the latter predominantly in Northeast and Southeast Asia, but both cultures are present in all three regions of Asia. Politically, while there are democratic countries such as India, South Korea, Japan, Thailand, the Philippines, Malaysia, and Indonesia, their democracy has been very fragile, especially in the last four countries, as extremist groups emerged as an alternative to electoral politics. Religious freedom is also threatened by authoritarian, one-party, and/or military governments such as China, North Korea, Vietnam, Myanmar, Laos, and Brunei. To elaborate a Christian theology appropriate to Asia as a whole it is helpful to highlight some key common elements of Christianities in the three regions even though it is necessary to pay close attention to the socio-political, economic, cultural, and religious contexts in which Christianity exists, not only in each of the three regions but also in each country.⁶

First, it has often been said that Christianity in Asia was and remains a foreign religion that was imported by Western missionaries. Historically, this is true of Christianity in all three regions of Asia. Christianity was brought to Asia by missionaries from Portugal (India, China, Macau, Vietnam, and Timor-Leste), Spain (the Philippines), the Netherlands (Taiwan and Indonesia), Britain (India, Hong Kong, Malaysia, and Singapore), France (Vietnam, Cambodia, Laos, and Thailand), and the United States (South Korea, Myanmar, and the Philippines). Perhaps the point of the observation about the foreign character of Christianity is that

⁶ For excellent surveys of Christianity in Asia, see Kenneth R. Ross, Daniel Jeyaraj, and Todd M. Johnson, eds., *Christianity in South and Central Asia* (Edinburgh: University of Edinburgh Press, 2019) and Kenneth R. Ross, Francis D. Alvarez, and Todd M. Johnson, eds., *Christianity in East and Southeast Asia*. Edinburgh: University of Edinburgh Press, 2020.

Christianity has not been thoroughly indigenized into the local cultures and contexts like other Asian religions and that some Christian denominations are currently still dependent on foreign financial aid and administrative authorities and do not subscribe to the Three-Self Principles, namely, self-governing, self-supporting, and self-propagating. This is especially true of the Catholic Church, with its organizational and juridical ties to the Vatican City State.

Secondly, connected with the foreignness of Christianity is the historical alliance between Christianity and colonialism in Asia. Missionaries from Portugal, Spain, Britain, France, and the United States came to evangelize Asian countries with the financial and political support of their colonizing countries. No doubt the Catholic Church benefited much from this arrangement; indeed, without the assistance of the Iberian empires, it would be very unlikely that the Church could have carried out its evangelizing mission in the new worlds of Latin America and Asia. Asian Christians must honestly acknowledge the colonial legacy of their Churches and the many privileges accrued to them, especially in terms of education, health care, and social services, as the best schools, universities, hospitals, and social institutions in their countries are owned or administered by Christians.

The third common feature of Asian Christianity is its existence amidst overwhelming poverty. While South Korea, Taiwan, Hong Kong, and Singapore are the four economic ‘Asian Tigers’ thanks to their rapid economic growth and an improved standard of living, and although Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, and Vietnam have recently reached the status of economic ‘Tiger Cubs,’ there are still millions of Asians living below poverty level, subsisting on less than US\$ 1.90 a day, and having little access to education, health care, and social services. Massive poverty is also worsened by the endemic corruption and graft by kleptocratic governments that steal public funds earmarked for the betterment of the living standards in their countries. Furthermore, while globalization has raised the

living standards in several Asian countries, its neoliberal market economy has widened the gap between the rich and the poor. This new form of colonialism is no less destructive of human dignity and human rights than the old one. Indeed, neocolonialism is more dangerous as its impact is not as visible as the old-time colonizers' occupation of their lands and exploitation of their natural resources. One of the most pernicious effects of the neoliberal economy is consumerism, which is the siren's song to youth and enslaves the consumers as they accumulate more and more things.

The fourth common element is ecological degradation in many Asian countries. There is an urgent need for Asian Christians to grasp the causal connection between the release of greenhouse gases (carbon dioxide, methane, nitrogen oxides, and others) into the atmosphere, the depletion of the ozone layer, global warming, the melting of the polar ice, the rise of the sea level on the one hand and human activities such as the burning of fossil fuel (coal, petroleum, and gas), deforestation, the dumping of industrial and nuclear waste and chemical products, and the increasing use of fertilizers, insecticides, fungicides, herbicides and agrottoxins on the other. The common tendency to attribute ecological destruction and natural disasters to divine punishment must be resisted. In addition, many Asian countries, for example, Indonesia and the Philippines, are located in the 'ring of fire,' with devastating volcanic eruptions. Furthermore, countries with a high percentage of their population living near rivers and the coastlines are frequent victims of the effects of climate change such as tsunamis, floods, and droughts that destroy the poor's livelihood and force them to migrate.

The fifth common feature of Christianity is its minority status in all Asian countries, except the Philippines and Timor-Leste. Asian Christians exist in Muslim-majority (Pakistan, Bangladesh, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Brunei), Hindu-majority (India), and Buddhist majority (South Korea, Thailand, Cambodia, Laos, Vietnam, and Sri Lanka) countries. This minority status makes

dialogue with the followers of other religions an existential imperative for Asian Christians. I will return to this issue in the last part of my lecture.

The sixth common feature of some Asian countries is co-existence with Communism. In self-declared Communist countries such as China, Vietnam, and North Korea, Christianity is no longer targeted for eradication as such but the Churches must be registered with the government, and their activities are regulated and restricted under the pretext of “national security” and “social unity.” In China, in particular, the Catholic Church must deal with the problem of two parallel Churches, the so-called official or registered Church and the underground or unregistered Church, especially the thorny issue of the nomination and ordination of bishops. In authoritarian countries, often under military regimes, religious repression and violations of human rights are committed not in the name of ideology but to maintain the government’s absolute power. In Muslim-majority countries such as Pakistan, Brunei, Indonesia, and Malaysia, religious freedom is constitutionally guaranteed but in practice, legal restrictions on religious practices are put in place against Christians. Even in democratic countries such as India, Malaysia, and Indonesia, especially when right-wing political movements and religious extremists are in power, there are the blasphemy law and prohibitions against conversion from Islam and Hinduism, the use of the term Allah for the Christian God, the distribution of bibles, missionary activities, and public celebration of Christian feasts.

The seventh common feature of Asian countries is ubiquitous migration. In the last fifty years, Asia has massively entered the global migration age. Rapid economic growth, the impact of globalization, social transformations, international and civil wars, and ecological disasters have accelerated the rate of migration of Asians from Asian countries to non-Asian countries, to other Asian countries (international migrants), and also within each country (internally displaced persons), especially due to the movement of

people from rural areas to the cities in search of work (urbanization). From the end of World War II and the dismantling of British, French, Dutch, and Japanese colonial empires to 1973, there were waves of returning colonists, often with their families of colonial subjects, to their respective countries, especially from Indonesia to Holland, from Vietnam to France, from Timor-Leste to Portugal, and from India to Britain. Also during these three decades, there were protracted wars in Korea and Vietnam that caused millions of people to leave the north for the south. During 1975-1989, after the oil boom, the Gulf region emerged as the new migration destination for Asian migrants, especially from India, Pakistan, and the Philippines. The end of the Vietnam War, with the victory of Communist North Vietnam over South Vietnam in 1975, saw hundreds of thousands of Vietnamese, Cambodians, and Laotians migrate to the U.S., Canada, Australia, and European countries. During 1989-2008, the increasing demand for lower-and higher-skilled workers in the Gulf region attracted a large number of Asian migrants. Also, there was intra-regional migration from poorer Southeast Asian countries like Indonesia, Vietnam, and the Philippines to richer Southeast Asian countries like Malaysia, Singapore, and Thailand and East Asian countries such as China, Japan, South Korea, and Taiwan. Since 2008 there has been an acceleration of extra-regional migration, especially from Indonesia and Myanmar, to the Gulf, North America, and Europe, and intra-regional migration, especially to East Asia and some countries of Southeast Asia. Recently there has been a forced displacement of Rohingyas from Myanmar and Uyghurs in Northwest China.

The eighth common feature of Asian countries is the oppressed status of women, economically, socio-politically, culturally, and religiously. Though significant improvements in women's condition have been made in several countries thanks to their struggle for equal rights, there are still severe restrictions based on their gender in education, employment, political rights, and religious functions, especially in Muslim-majority countries and

those with patriarchal cultures. The Christian Churches in Asia as a whole have exacerbated this anti-woman ethos with their male-dominated structures and practices.

Future Asian Theologies: Tasks and Orientations

Christian theology is the critical and systematic understanding of Jesus' message about the reign of God as it is communicated and lived by the Church in different times and places. There are thus two constitutive elements in the making of theology, one that is constant and permanent, namely, Jesus' message, and the other by nature changeable and varied, namely, its transmission and practice by Christians in various contexts. Of course, Jesus' message itself, though permanent and constant, is not a context-free reality descending straight from heaven as it were; rather, like the eternal Son of God made flesh as a Jew in Palestine, his message, as recorded in the New Testament, is already contextualized in different cultures, namely, Jewish and Greek. Consequently, it is more accurate to understand theology as an intercontextual or intercultural critical study of the encounter between the cultures in which Jesus' message has been embodied and the new cultures in which it is to be inculturated again. There are in theology both the transcendent or universal message of Jesus about the reign of God and the historicized or particular realization of that message at different times and in various locations throughout the world.

Doing theology in this way involves three interrelated steps. The first step, which may be called the "socio-analytic mediation" of the theological discipline, seeks to ascertain the empirical facts as they are, as objectively and as truthfully as possible, as the context for theology, as I have done above. The second step, which may be called the "hermeneutical mediation," interprets the empirical data in the light of the Bible and Christian Tradition; and vice versa, it interprets the Bible and the Christian Tradition in the light of the empirical data obtained in the socio-analytic mediation to yield a theological hypothesis or theory. The third step, the "practical

mediation,” seeks to embody the theological answer in the practice of the Christian community, which practice, in turn, generates new data for the socio-analytic mediation, and the processes of theological hermeneutic mediation and practical mediation begin all over again.⁷ In what follows, it is not of course possible to elaborate the hermeneutical and practical mediations of an Asian theology in detail. I will only indicate some of the tasks and orientations of such a theology in the light of the data discussed above.

First, the widespread and dehumanizing poverty in several Asian countries must be the constant concern of Asian Churches. This poverty has been exacerbated by neocolonialist globalization, government corruption, anti-democratic militaristic regime, increasing urbanization, and ecological degradation, which prevent social, political, and economic projects from attaining their goals of bringing about well-being to the most marginalized citizens. The work of abolishing poverty in favour of justice and integral development has been repeatedly advocated by the FABC as an intrinsic part of the mission of the Church and must be a fundamental theme of Asian theology.⁸

Second, connected with poverty is the issue of migration. Several Asian countries are countries of emigration, especially Pakistan, Nepal, the Philippines, Vietnam, Indonesia, and Myanmar. Churches must set up programs to prepare emigrants before their departure, connect with them while they are abroad, and assist the families that are left behind. Emigration cannot be eliminated, but efforts must be made by both the government and the Churches to reduce the “culture of emigration,” the feminization of labour export, sex trafficking, and the misuse of remittances in the

⁷ On this triple mediation, see Peter C. Phan, *Christianity with an Asian Face: Asian American Theology in the Making*. Maryknoll, N.Y.: Orbis Books, 2004. 26-46.

⁸ See in particular the works of Aloysius Pieris, Michael Amaladoss, and Felix Wilfred.

emigration countries. Theologically, a theology of migration must be elaborated in which God is shown to be the Primordial Migrant, Jesus the Paradigmatic Migrant, the Holy Spirit the Power of Migration, and the Church as a community of migrants.⁹

Third, the work to make Christianity a truly Asian religion through comprehensive inculturation or contextualization, already well underway in several countries, for example, India, South Korea, and the Philippines, should be assiduously continued and expanded to all aspects of the church life in all countries. Here theology has an irreplaceable role. Beyond classical resources such as philosophy and religion, such theological inculturation must take into account the socio-political and economic contexts, cultural artefacts, and digital social media. In this way, Asian Christianity can effectively shed its colonial heritage and its foreign character. While Protestants, Evangelicals, and Pentecostals devote their resources to translating the Bible into hundreds of local languages, Catholics focus on adapting the liturgy and worship to the local cultures, making use of indigenous music, song, dance, rituals, practices of popular religion, and customs. A theology of inculturation must be developed in which the relation between the Gospel and culture is carefully analysed, the dynamic equivalences between the Christian beliefs and the beliefs of other religions are explored, and the ways to express and live the Christian faith in different local contexts are put into practice.¹⁰

Fourth, the nature of the Christian mission must be thoroughly reconceived. Mission or evangelism is understood and practiced

⁹ See Peter C. Phan, ed., *Christian Theology in the Age of Migration: Implications for World Christianity*. Lanham: Lexington Books, 2020 and the many writings of Gemma T. Cruz.

¹⁰ The literature by Asian theologians on inculturation is immense. Beside the works of Pieris, Amaladoss, Wilfred, and many others, see Peter C. Phan, *In Our Own Tongues: Perspectives from Asia on Mission and Inculturation* Maryknoll, N.Y.: Orbis Books, 2004.

very differently by Christians in Asia. Evangelicals, Pentecostals/Charismatics, and Independents understand mission as consisting mainly in preaching to non-Christians with the ultimate goal of converting and baptizing them. As mentioned above, this kind of mission is prohibited in some Muslim-majority countries. On the other hand, other Churches understand mission as bearing witness, by word and deed, to the Christian faith with the goal not primarily to convert non-Christian individuals, though this is not excluded, but to bring the reality and values of God's kingdom to the world. Christian mission is not only *missio ad gentes*, with non-Christians as the objects of the Christian's evangelism but also, and above all, *missio inter gentes*, that is, a mutual mission to one another, with Christians and non-Christians "converting" one another toward the kingdom of God, and *missio cum gentibus*, that is, mission carried by Christians together with non-Christians for the coming of the reign of God. This dialogue is particularly urgent between Christians and Muslims in Asia as both religions are forecast to be the two major religions in Asia. A peaceful relation between the two groups is essential for the well-being of Asia, especially in countries such as India, Thailand, the Philippines, and Indonesia.¹¹

Fifth, given the enormous growth of Evangelicals, Pentecostals/Charismatics, and Independents in Asia, a robust theology of the Holy Spirit (pneumatology) is urgently needed, not only for the dialogue between them and the other branches of Christianity (ecumenical dialogue) but also for a positive appreciation of the role of non-Christian religions in God's plan of salvation (interreligious dialogue). In Catholic theology, in Asia as well as elsewhere, a Christocentric, even Christonomic theology has been developed extensively; as a result, an exclusivist approach is usually adopted in the theology of religion. To redress the balance, a

¹¹ On this understanding of mission, see Peter C. Phan, *The Joy of Religious Pluralism: A Personal Journey*. Maryknoll, N.Y.: Orbis Books, 2017, 129-164.

pneumatological Christology or Christological pneumatology is urgently needed to acknowledge the salvific presence of God in non-Christian religions. In this way, St. Irenaeus’s celebrated image of God the Father (*Theos*) acting in the world always with two hands, the Word (*Logos*) and the Spirit (*Pneuma*), and not one *or* the other, is made into the leitmotif of Christian theology.¹²

Sixth, the widespread destruction of the environment in almost all Asian countries by both natural catastrophes and human abuses of natural resources which produces climate change and global warming urgently calls for a comprehensive theology of creation and ecology that moves beyond “natural” and human/social” ecology to “integral” ecology. In this respect, Pope Francis’s encyclical *Laudato Si’* is a magna carta that provides rich insights on solidarity, sustainability, and subsidiarity; on the links among ecology, migration, economics, and politics; on capitalism, consumerism, and the “throwaway culture”; on work and human relationships; on technology, energy, and recycling; and on food and water.¹³

Seventh, interreligious dialogue must be seriously undertaken in Christian-majority as well as Christian-minority countries. This is done in four areas, as frequently advocated by the FABC, namely, sharing daily life, collaboration for the common good, theological reflection, and sharing spiritual experiences. This interreligious dialogue not only promotes a deeper understanding and acceptance of the religious “Other” but is also an effective means to reduce religious extremism, radicalism, and violence in Asia. A theology of interreligious dialogue must go beyond the three paradigms of

¹² On a Christology and pneumatology on the basis of Irenaeus’s metaphor of the “two hands” of God, see Peter C. Phan, *The Joy of Religious Pluralism*, 51-74.

¹³ On an ecological theology for Asia based on Pope Francis’s *Laudato Si’*, see Peter C. Phan, *Asian Christianities: History, Theology, Practice* Maryknoll, N.Y.: Orbis Books, 2018. 288-302.

exclusivism, inclusivism, and pluralism in which Christianity is taken as the norm to evaluate the truth and value of other religions which are judged to be true and holy only to the extent they conform to Christianity, to be “fulfilled” by it, or as merely stepping-stones to Christianity. Rather, the dialogue among the religions must be a sincere, respectful, and humble undertaking to witness truthfully to others what one believes and practices without claiming that one’s religion is the only true one or the best, a claim that is epistemologically impossible to prove, and with readiness to share with others the truths and values of one’s religion, to learn from the truths and practices of the religions of the partners-in-dialogue, to correct the errors and deficiencies of one’s religion, and to be complemented and enriched by others.¹⁴

Eighth, though a vibrant feminist theology has been developed in Asia, especially in India, the Philippines, and Korea, it is far from gaining widespread acceptance and has not been made an integral part of the theological curriculum in almost all Christian denominations, notably the Catholic, Orthodox, Evangelical, and Pentecostal Churches. The necessity of feminist theology for Asia is made all the more urgent by the fact Church life is nurtured by a large number of female workers, though mostly in subordinate positions. Such feminist theology should not derive its inspiration only from Western theories but also from abundant Asian resources, both cultural and religious.¹⁵

In sum, a Christian theology that is appropriate for South, Northeast, and Southeast Asia must begin from their contemporary socio-political, economic, cultural, and religious contexts and the common

¹⁴ On this concept of interreligious dialogue, see Peter C. Phan, *Being Religious Interreligiously: Asian Perspectives on Interfaith Dialogue*. Maryknoll, N.Y.: Orbis Books, 2004.

¹⁵ See Kwok Pui-lan, *Introducing Asian Feminist Theology* (Cleveland: Pilgrim Press, 2000) and *Post Colonial Imagination & Feminist Theology*. Louisville, KY: Westminster John Knox Press, 2005.

challenges that these contexts pose to Christianity. Christian theology interprets these data in the light of the Gospel and the Gospel in the light of these data. I contend that to meet the challenges of Asia today contemporary Asian theology must develop a theology of liberation, migration, inculturation, mission, the Holy Spirit, ecology interreligious dialogue and feminist theology. I have also indicated the main outlines and orientations of these eight theologies, with the full awareness that they should be adapted to the particular conditions of each region and each country. I am deeply aware that I am not proposing new paths for Asian theology but simply systematizing the approaches and ideas of Asian theologians, more for the benefit of theologians of other continents, especially the West, who may still resist them.¹⁶

Pope Francis and Interreligious Encounter

With the election of a new pope there inevitably arises, at least among Catholics, the hope that he will bring needed changes in the Church, or the fear that he will deviate from the unchangeable Tradition. What kinds of changes, or fears, are harboured depend of course on the ones who hope or fear, and on the kind of pope who is elected. In 2013, hopes and fears were heightened by the fact that Jorge Bergoglio is the first Jesuit and the first South American to be elected to the papacy. On the right, there was anxiety that he might not pursue the restorationist program of his two predecessors, John Paul II and Benedict XVI, and will enact instead the Latin American liberal agenda. On the left, it was hoped that Francis would complete the unfinished businesses of Vatican II, including the reform of the Roman Curia, optional priestly celibacy, ordination of women, and various issues of sexual ethics. In addition, the new pope is expected to resolve urgent recent problems such as clerical sex abuse, gay

¹⁶ Note that I have not mentioned a specific theology in response to Communist and socialist ideologies, and this is of set purpose. I do not believe that the most effective counterresponse to these ideologies is a theoretical discussion of the metaphysical “proofs” of God’s existence. Rather the Church’s convincing “argument” for the belief in God is a relentless struggle for equality and justice, especially in favour of the poor and the oppressed.

marriage, the Vatican's financial scandals, the impact of globalization, climate change, and ecological destruction.

As it turned out, to the surprise of both conservatives and liberals, Bergoglio, who took il Poverello of Assisi not only as his name but also as his role model, began his pontificate by unostentatiously dropping the papal princely lifestyle, instituted sweeping changes in the Roman Curia, made many apostolic visits to far-flung places, participated collegially in several synods of bishops, and issued a series of ground-breaking documents, on the mission of Church (*The Joy of the Gospel*), ecology (*Laudato Si'* and *Querida Amazonia*), love in the family (*Amoris Laetitia*), and social friendship (*Fratelli Tutti*). Here I will not consider all the issues mentioned above but only one part of Francis's agenda that is very important to him but on which he has not devoted a full-fledged and comprehensive document. I refer to interreligious dialogue, or to use Francis' preferred expression, interreligious *encounter*.

As is well known, with *Nostra Aetate*, the Catholic Church made a volte-face in its assessment of other religions. Though the shortest of all the 16 conciliar documents, with only 1,141 words in 41 sentences and 5 paragraphs in the original Latin, the declaration improbably became the magna carta of the Church's relations with non-Christian religions. Of course, there lacked no vigorous opposition to the various postconciliar initiatives and theologies of interreligious dialogue, as the condemnation of several theological writings on religious pluralism and the declaration *Dominus Iesus* of the Congregation for the Doctrine of the Faith (2000) under Ratzinger/Benedict XVI readily show. Francis inherited a contentious and ambiguous legacy on interreligious dialogue but has consistently and firmly pledged to promote mutual understanding between the Catholic Church and other religions.

So far, there is still a dearth of scholarly investigations of Pope Francis's activities and thought on interreligious dialogue.¹⁷ In general, Francis

¹⁷ A significant study of Pope Francis's understanding of interreligious dialogue in English is Harold Kasimow, Alan Race, and Rabbi Abraham Skorka, eds., *Pope Francis and Interreligious Dialogue: Religious Thinkers Engage with Recent Papal Initiatives* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan,

approaches interreligious dialogue primarily as a pastor and a practical theologian and not as a systematic theologian, like Benedict XVI, concerned with expounding on the theological issues implicated in the dialogue between Christianity and non-Christian religions. Here I will not chronicle Francis’s activities in favour of interreligious dialogue, especially his many meetings with the leaders of other religions, in particular the Grand Imam Ahmed Al-Tayyeb of Egypt, with whom he signed the historic “Document on Human Fraternity for World Peace and Living Together.” Rather I will reflect on the pronouncements Francis made on interreligious encounter on disparate occasions to see if they open the door for re-thinking Catholic traditional teachings on the major issues involving interreligious dialogue.

One of Pope Francis’s key refrains is that interreligious dialogue is an indispensable and effective way to resolve all kinds of conflicts (not just religious), restore peace and harmony, build up social justice, and preserve ecological integrity. Already in his very first writing, *Evangelii Gaudium* (EG, nos. 238-258), Francis speaks of dialogue in three areas to promote full human development and the common good: dialogue with states, dialogue with society, including cultures and the sciences, and dialogue with non-Catholic Christians (ecumenical dialogue) and non-Christian believers (interreligious dialogue). In his latest encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* Francis comes closest to formulating his theology of interreligious dialogue (FT, nos. 271-285.) It is most noteworthy that in both documents Francis places interreligious dialogue in the context of *social* dialogue, the goal of which is “to establish friendship, peace and harmony, and to share spiritual and moral values and experiences in a spirit of truth and love” (FT, no. 271).

This approach is Francis’s both strengths and weaknesses. On the one hand, it harnesses the energies of all religions to achieve concrete and tangible goals, not least the elimination of religious violence. On the other hand, it moves away from doctrinal dialogue and leaves unexamined and

2018). Leo Lefebure’s final assessment (303-328) is particularly insightful.

unchanged the *theological* claims that have fuelled suspicion, hatred, and violence in the first place. Among these claims are, for instance,

- The uniqueness and universality of Jesus as saviour;
- The truth and superiority of Christianity over all other religions; the divine origin of Christian revelation, sacred books, and rituals in contrast to the purely human character of those of other religions;
- The missionary obligation to “proclaim” the Gospel to all;
- The necessity of converting other believers and unbelievers to Christianity, and more specifically, to the Catholic Church, which alone and exclusively has all the means of salvation.

Admittedly, these theological claims, central in traditional Catholic theology of religion, *by themselves* do not lead to violence but when backed up by Christians’ superior economic, political, military, and colonial powers, which were not rare, together they made a combustible mix to ignite oppression and war against other believers and unbelievers. Left untouched, they threaten to derail the very objectives Francis sets for interreligious encounters.

To date, Francis has not dealt explicitly with any of these Christian claims. He has simply repeated Vatican II’s teaching on the possibility of salvation for all, including non-Christian and unbelievers, as contained especially in *Lumen Gentium*, no. 16, *Ad Gentes*, no. 9, and *Nostra Aetate*. He insists that “evangelization and interreligious dialogue, far from being opposed, mutually support and nourish each other” and that a “facile syncretism” must be avoided in interreligious dialogue (*EG*, no. 251). He maintains that in interreligious dialogue Christians must hold on to their “Christian identity” (*FT*, no. 277). His continued use of traditional expressions to designate Christian mission such as “proclamation” implies that the Church has the whole truth to teach non-Christians

with authority (“proclaim”) and has little if anything to learn from them.

On the other hand, some of Francis’ statements seem to open the door, however slightly, for revising and modifying the current teachings of the Catholic Church on the issues listed above. He acknowledges that God’s work in non-Christians “tends to produce signs and rites, sacred expressions which in turn brings others to a communitarian experience of journeying towards God” (*EG*, no. 254). In other words, it is God who establishes what we call non-Christian “religions” and therefore non-Christian religions lie within the divine economy of salvation. Francis even calls them “channels which the Holy Spirit raises up to liberate non-Christians from atheistic immanentism or from purely individual religious experiences,” even though they “lack the meaning and efficacy of the sacraments instituted by Christ” (*EG*, no. 254). “Channels” used by the Holy Spirit may be regarded as the equivalents of Christian “sacraments.”

Furthermore, Francis explicitly acknowledges that interreligious dialogue can be “a process in which, by mutual listening, both parts [Christian and non-Christian] can be purified and enriched” (*EG*, no. 250). The pope pointedly notes that Christians can benefit from the teachings and practices of other religions to be better Christians (*EG*, no. 254). In this way, Christian mission is not to be understood as a one-directional activity of Christians to non-Christians (*missio ad gentes*) but a reciprocal “evangelization” among other believers (*missio inter gentes*) and with them (*missio cum gentibus*). As for conversion, Pope Francis says that in fraternal/sisterly dialogue “with my identity and my empathy, my openness, I walk with the other. I don’t try to make him come over me. I don’t proselytize.” He acknowledges that God will move hearts and someone will ask for baptism, sometimes not. But always let us walk together. This is the heart of dialogue” (On the 6th Asian Youth Day Meeting with the Bishops of Asia, 17 August 2014).

One of Francis' favorite images for interreligious dialogue and the "culture of encounter" is the polyhedron "whose different sides for a variegated unity in which the whole is greater than the part" and the sum of its parts (*FT*, no. 215). He strongly urges that we create "a social covenant": "Such a covenant also demands the realization that some things may have to be renounced for the common good. No one can possess the whole truth or satisfy his or her every desire since that pretension would lead to nullifying others by denying their rights" (*FT*, 111). Should not this statement be applied to the Church as a whole as well, and if so, which of its traditional teachings on other religions will have to be "renounced" or at least modified "for the common good"?

It is not the task of the pope to make dogmatic pronouncements on these still-unresolved issues, but at least his statements leave the door open and encourage theologians to explore them in the context of religious pluralism, especially in Asia. In this endeavour they are guided by Pope Francis's four principles: first, time is greater than space; second, unity prevails over conflict; third, realities are more important than ideas; and fourth, the whole is greater than the sum of its parts (*EG*, nos. 222-237). Accordingly, all the truths must be contextualized in their history and development; doctrinal differences must not lead to division and conflict; ideas can never exhaustively capture reality and must be revised constantly to fully reflect reality; and, individual truths must be seen as part of a whole that is greater than each of them and gives validity to them. Meanwhile, as theological explorations are being carried out, the Church must exercise its evangelizing mission in the only way possible, namely, sincere and humble dialogue and fraternal encounter, to build up justice and peace, as Pope Francis and the Federation of Asian Bishops' Conferences never tire to insist. In this way, Asian Catholicism and Asian theologians can make a significant contribution to a new understanding of the nature of the Church, its mission, and its relations to other religions.

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